

DETERMINATION OF THERMODYNAMIC SURFACE CHARACTERISTICS OF CARBON NANOTUBES VIA INVERSE GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY METHOD

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Abstract

Inverse gas chromatography method is widely used for the characterization of polymers and surfactants that are capable to offer useful information to predict miscibility of polymer composites. However adaption of IGC to carbon nanotubes (CNTs) is still challenging due to many problems arising in establishment and there are only limited reports about CNTs. Thus we researched the thermodynamic surface characteristics of CNTs study. And we confirmed that the IGC method can be successfully applied for various CNTs to determine unknown thermodynamic surface characteristics, including solubility parameter in particular.

1. Introduction

CNTs are attractive candidate for reinforcing filler in CNT based composites.[1] However, due to the strong Van der Waals interaction between CNTs, they tend to agglomerate and form bundles, which hinder good dispersion in surrounding media. So their compatibility with common polymer matrix is very limited and phase separation, a cause of performance deterioration, occurs in composites.[2] To enhance the miscibility, modification of surface characteristics with various functional groups has been most widely adopted. However, finding suitable pair of modified CNT/matrix for a given type of CNTs still entirely relies on the experimental trials and errors. To overcome this situation, it is required to find appropriate guidelines or parameters enabling it to predict the dispersion behavior of CNTs which cannot be determined by general

surface characterization method such as XPS, FT-IR etc.

In this research, we introduced an IGC method. IGC is a powerful method which offers essential thermodynamic surface characteristic information of column packing materials, including surface tension, interaction parameter and solubility parameter. This method has advantages for investigating the characteristics of solid surfaces in powder form and has been widely used to the characterizing of the surface properties of polymers. And recently it is applied for determination of surface characteristics of carbon nanomaterials. However adaption of IGC on CNTs is still challenging and only a few studies have been published by this time. This is because strong dispersive interaction and high specific surface area result in weak and distorted retention chromatograms. [3]

Herein we tried to find method to avoid such problems, and moreover thermal decomposition of the surface functional groups in the case of surface modified CNTs. Then we determine thermodynamic parameters representing the surface characteristics, including Hansen Solubility Parameters.

2. Theory

Surface characteristics determined by IGC are calculated with retention volume obtained by symmetrical peak of chromatogram under ideal dilute condition of probe molecules with next eq. 1 [3]

$$V_g = \frac{jF(t_r - t_m)}{m} \frac{T}{273.2K} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

(V_g : specific retention volume, F : flow rate of carrier gas, t_r : retention time of probe, t_m : void retention time measured by non-interacting marker, T : column temperature, m : mass of stationary phase (packing material in column), j : James-Martin correction factor [4])

Adsorption free energy ΔG_A can be calculated from V_g using the following relationship

$$-\Delta G_A = RT \ln\left(\frac{V_g P_0}{SB_0}\right) \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

(R : gas constant, S : specific surface area, P_0 : reference partial pressure of probes = $1.013 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$, B_0 : reference bidimensional spreading pressure of the adsorbed probe = $3.38 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Nm}^{-1}$)

Dispersive surface tension γ^D is obtained by following relation equation [5]

$$\gamma_S^D = \left(\frac{\Delta G_{CH_2}}{2N_A a_{CH_2}} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\gamma_{CH_2}} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

(ΔG_{CH_2} : adsorption free energy per mole of CH_2 groups of aliphatic hydrocarbon, N_A : Avogadro's number, a_{CH_2} : cross sectional area of a methylene group (0.06 nm^2), γ_{CH_2} : surface energy of infinite polyethylene chain,)

ΔG_{CH_2} and γ_{CH_2} can be represented with following equation.[6]

$$\Delta G_{CH_2} = -RT \ln\left(\frac{V_{n+1}}{V_n}\right) \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

$$\gamma_{CH_2} = 35.6 + 0.058(20 - T) \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

(V_n , V_{n+1} : retention volume of aliphatic hydrocarbon of carbon number n , $n+1$)

Using the model developed by Karger et al. [7], the Hansen solubility parameters of solids can be calculated from IGC data with ΔE_A as follow:

$$-\Delta E_A = V_p (\delta_d^p \delta_d^s + \delta_p^p \delta_p^s + \delta_h^p \delta_h^s) \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

(V_p : molar volume of probes, δ : solubility parameter, d , p , h : dispersion, polar, hydrogen-bonding component of solubility parameter, P : solubility parameter of probes, S : solubility parameter of stationary phase)

Assumed that the change in volume on adsorption of infinite dilute gas probe on stationary phase is zero,

ΔE_A is approximately identical with ΔH_A , adsorption enthalpy, calculated from slope of plot of $\Delta G_A/T$ vs $1/T$.

By adjusting multi linear regression method to eq. 6 with known solubility parameter of probes, Hansen solubility parameter of stationary phase can be obtained.

3. Experimental

3.1 Materials

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (<96% carbon contents) are produced using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method by JEIO Co., Ltd. (denoted APMWCNT).

3.2 Inverse Gas Chromatography

IGC chromatograms were recorded on a Perkin Elmer Clarus 600 Gas Chromatograph (Perkin Elmer, USA) with a thermal conductivity detector.

CNTs were packed into a stainless steel tube of 1/4 inch in diameter to prepare columns. Each end of the columns was plugged with silane-treated glass wool to fix the stationary phase. The columns were stabilized in the GC system under a helium flow to eliminate pre-adsorbed volatile impurities if any.

To find optimum working conditions of IGC, a relationship between adsorption thermodynamic parameters determined with operating variables including the quantity of the injected probe molecules, and column temperature was investigated. And the validity of conditions was confirmed by a linear relationship of enthalpy or dispersive surface tension.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Data correction

As shown in Fig. 1, the adsorption free energy increases exponentially with decreasing quantity of the injected probe molecules. It is well known that as the concentration of the probe decreases, the retention chromatogram becomes more symmetrical. As denoted above theory section, determination of surface characteristics by IGC should be performed under ideal dilute condition. In this condition, chromatogram shows symmetrical peak and retention time doesn't depend on quantity of probe.

Fig.1. Injected quantity of chloroform vs adsorption free energy of chloroform on APMWCNTs.

When the concentration is infinitely dilute, it is at the zero surface coverage (ZSC) condition, which is required to determine the surface characteristics precisely. Based on this definition of ZSC, an extrapolation to y-axis in Fig. 1 can yield the adsorption free energy at ZSC, which make it possible to determine the precise thermodynamic surface characteristics

Fig. 2 Reciprocal of temperature vs adsorption free energy divided by temperature (50°C ~250 °C)

Indeed, Fig. 2 clearly shows a linear relationship between the reciprocal of temperature and adsorption free energy divided by temperature. The results of Figs. 1 and 2 indicate that it is possible to determine the surface characteristics of CNTs even at low temperature whereby the ZSC condition is met.

4.2. Dispersive surface tension

Fig.3. Dispersive surface tension of APMWCNTs (200~240°C).

Dispersive surface tension of CNTs were obtained by calculation of above eq. 3~5. For APMWCNTs, it showed 90.7mJ/m^2 under 200°C condition with linear relationship between temperatures. And it showed similar results with reported values about different type of as-received CNTs or graphite powders [5].

4.3. Hansen solubility parameters

Hansen solubility parameters of APMWCNTs were determined by multi linear regression with adsorption enthalpy of various probes. Obtained data were $\delta_d=19.7$, $\delta_p=4.1$, $\delta_h=5.7$ (unit: $\text{MPa}^{1/2}$) respectively. It is compared with reported value which is obtained by calculation from center of Hansen sphere radius with observation of sedimentation behavior of CNT dispersion which reported $\delta_d=19.8$, $\delta_p=6.1$, $\delta_h=4.3$ [8]

From the results, Hansen solubility parameters obtained by IGC showed relatively similar with the value obtained by Hansen sphere radius. To predict the dispersion property of CNTs in solvents by comparing the parameters of CNTs and solvents, they showed almost similar tendency with common solvents. So we conclude that prediction of the dispersion behavior of CNTs with IGC is acceptable

5. Conclusions

Thermodynamic surface characteristics of CNTs determined by IGC were studied. To be met ZSC condition, Effects of IGC condition on the surface characteristics of CNTs were examined. With this condition, surface characteristics of CNTs could be obtained and hence the dispersion behavior of CNTs in solvents is possibly predicted.

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